

Analytical Applications of DEAPG as Gravimetric Reagent-I Estimation of Hg(II)

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p-Diethylaminoanil of phenyl glyoxal (abbreviated as DEAPG) precipitates Mercury(II) quantitatively and gives dark brown complex at pH 9.8 by adding double theoretical quantity of the ligand. It can be used for the gravimetric estimation of Hg(II) either alone or in presence of foreign ions.

APERUSAL of literature on gravimetric analysis of metals reveals that many large organic compounds have been used in the inorganic quantitative estimations but ketoanils¹⁻³ have been rarely employed as precipitating reagents. Moreover gravimetric determination of Hg(II) was done by Nigam and Tewari⁴ using 1-imino-3 thioisoin-doline, Kaushik and Prasad⁵ using Sodium meta periodate and Chaudhary and Das⁶ using Cyclopentanone-2-carboxy anilide but no attempt has been made in the quantitative estimation of this ion by employing ketoanil (DEAPG) as precipitating agent so far. The present paper aims at using new ligand *p*-diethylaminoanil of phenylglyoxal for the gravimetric determination of Hg(II). The work incorporated in this paper describes the suitable conditions for the precipitation of metal ions by the ligand.

Experimental

Stock solution of metal chloride was prepared by dissolving pure compound in alcohol and was used after standardisation by standard methods⁷. Standard solution of ligand was prepared by dissolving its directly weighed quantity in the same medium. All the reagents and chemicals used were of either B.D.H. or E. Merck, A.R. and G.R. grades respectively. Ligand was prepared by method reported by Verma⁸.

The pH of the solution was adjusted by using hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide. Phillips pH meter with glass and saturated calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements. G4-sintered glass crucibles (JENA) were used for gravimetric estimations.

In mercuric chloride solution, reagent was added very slowly with constant stirring till in slight

excess. The quantitative reaction was ensured by adjusting pH with the solution of acid and alkali. Reaction mixture was left for four hours (preferably overnight) and was collected on sintered glass crucible. The precipitate was washed with ether several times to remove excess of reagent and was dried to constant weight.

Dark brown complex was soluble in acetone, acetonitrile and alcohol (after heating) while insoluble in benzene, carbontetrachloride, petroleum ether and ether. It was decomposed by conc. nitric and sulphuric Acids.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH Reagent Concentration and Temperature :

In order to know the suitable conditions for the quantitative precipitation of Hg(II) with DEAPG, the precipitation of Hg(II)-DEAPG complex was carried out in the pH range from 7.8 to 12.0 by the addition of different quantity of the precipitant. After purification precipitates were dried and weighed from 50-130°. Data reported in Table 1 show that the weights of the precipitate found were almost corresponding to theoretical values of Hg(II)-DEAPG complex at 9.8 pH in the temperature range of 70-80° by adding double theoretical quantity of the ligand. Complex was found to be stable upto 140°.

Quantitative Gravimetric Estimation :

Under the above-mentioned conditions of pH, concentration of ligand and the temperature, gravimetric estimation of different quantities of Hg(II) were performed and results are noted in Table 2.

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH, REAGENT CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Observations at different pH (16.042mg Hg(II)≡ 41.153mg Complex taken)		Observations at different Concentrations of reagent (16.042mg Hg(II)≡ 41.153mg complex taken)		Observations at different temperatures (16.042mg Hg(II)≡ 41.153mg complex taken)	
Weight of precipitate (mg)	pH	Weight of precipitate (mg)	reagent added (mg)	Weight of precipitate (mg)	Temperature °C
28.2	7.8	40.0	25.2	43.8	50
35.2	8.2	40.0	28.0	42.6	60
37.8	8.7	40.4	33.6	42.8	65
39.0	9.2	40.8	36.4	41.4	70
39.0	9.6	40.6	39.2	41.4	75
40.6	9.7	41.2	42.0	41.4	80
41.0	9.8	41.2	44.8	41.0	90
41.0	10.0	41.0	47.6	40.4	100
38.8	10.5	40.4	50.4	40.6	110
37.0	11.0	39.4	53.2	39.6	120
35.2	12.0	38.2	56.0	39.0	130

TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF MERCURY WITH DEAPG

Hg taken (mg)	Weight of Complex (mg)	Hg found (mg)	Error (%)
10.02	25.6	9.98	-0.40
12.03	30.8	12.00	+0.24
16.04	41.2	16.06	+0.12
20.05	51.4	20.04	-0.05
24.06	61.8	24.09	+0.12
28.07	72.0	28.06	-0.03
32.08	82.4	32.12	+0.12
40.11	102.8	40.08	-0.07
48.13	123.4	48.10	-0.06
60.16	154.6	60.26	+0.16

Effect of Foreign Ions :

There was no interference by the addition of different quantities of following foreign ions on the precipitation of Hg(II) done in suitable conditions as are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF MERCURY IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

Hg taken (mg)	Foreign ion added (mg)	Weight of Hg Complex (mg)
16.042	F ⁻ (40)	41.6
16.042	Cl ⁻ (30)	41.6
16.042	Br ⁻ (20)	40.8
16.042	I ⁻ (30)	40.8
16.042	SO ₄ ⁻² (25)	41.4
16.042	NO ₃ ⁻ (20)	40.8
16.042	Pd ⁺² (30)	40.2
16.042	Au ⁺³ (25)	41.8

There are certain cations like Sn(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) which interfered in the estimation of Hg(II).

Conclusion :

The analytical data indicate that DEAPG effectively be used as a gravimetric reagent for Hg(II). It is easy to filter and bring the precipitate to constant weight within a period of two hours or so.

On account of high molecular weight of Hg(II)-DEAPG complex and low conversion factor for mercury makes the reagent (DEAPG) useful in the determination of micro quantities of metal. The precision and accuracy was found within the permissible limits.

In the light of above facts reagent DEAPG may be recommended as a promising gravimetric reagent for Mercury(II).

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